

Topological Polynomials in Fuzzy Hamiltonian Graph

N. K. Raut

Ex. Head, Dept. of Physics, Sunderrao Solanke Mahavidyalaya Majalgaon, Dist. Beed, (M.S.) INDIA

Corresponding Author – N. K. Raut

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Abstract:

A fuzzy graph $G = (\sigma, \mu)$ is a pair of functions of membership values of vertices and edges. A fuzzy Hamiltonian graph is a connected fuzzy graph containing a fuzzy cycle that visits every vertex exactly once, except for the starting and ending vertex coincide. The first and second Zagreb polynomial for fuzzy Hamiltonian graph are defined as: $M_1(G, x) = \sum_{u \in V} x^{\sigma(u) \cdot (d_G(u))^2}$ and $M_2(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E} x^{\frac{1}{2}[\sigma(u)d_G(u) + \sigma(v)d_G(v)]}$ respectively, where $d_G(u)$ is the degree of the vertex u and $\sigma(u)$ is the membership value of the vertex u in G . In this paper first, second Zagreb polynomials, hyper first, second Zagreb polynomials, forgotten polynomial, harmonic polynomial and Randic polynomial are investigated for fuzzy Hamiltonian graph.

Keywords: Degree, Hamiltonian cycle, Hamiltonian path, Fuzzy Hamiltonian graph, membership value.

Introduction:

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph consisting of a non-empty finite set V of elements called vertices and a finite set E of ordered pairs of distinct vertices called edges. In Fuzzy set theory we assign a membership value to each element of the set which ranges from 0 to 1. The underlying crisp graph of a fuzzy graph $G = (\sigma, \mu)$ is denoted by $G^* = (\mu^*, \sigma^*)$ where $\sigma^* = \{v \in V | \sigma(v) > 0\}$ and $\mu^* = \{(u, v) \in V \times V | \mu(u, v) > 0\}$. A fuzzy graph $G = (\sigma, \mu)$ is a pair of functions $\sigma: V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\mu: V \times V \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that for all $u, v \in V$, $\mu(u, v) \leq \sigma(u) \wedge \sigma(v)$ and μ is a symmetric fuzzy relation on σ . Here $\sigma(v)$ and $\mu(u, v)$ represent the membership values of the vertex v and of the edge (u, v) respectively [1-5]. A fuzzy graph $G: (\sigma, \mu)$ is said to be complete if $\mu(u, v) = \sigma(u) \wedge \sigma(v)$ for all u and v .

A Hamiltonian path is a path in an undirected or directed graph that visits each vertex exactly once. A Hamiltonian circuit is a Hamiltonian path that is a cycle. A cycle passing

through all the vertices of a graph is called a Hamiltonian cycle. A graph containing a Hamiltonian cycle is called a Hamiltonian graph. If the last edge of a Hamiltonian cycle is dropped, we get a Hamiltonian path. A connected fuzzy graph $G (\sigma, \mu)$ is said to be a fuzzy Hamiltonian graph if there exists a fuzzy cycle which covers all the nodes of fuzzy graph $G (\sigma, \mu)$ exactly once except the terminal nodes [6-7]. The problem of finding Hamiltonian cycles is named after William Rowan Hamilton, an Irish mathematician who was a big fan of the dodecahedron (the 3D shape whose sides are twelve pentagons) [8]. All vertices and edges in the Hamiltonian cycle has positive membership values.

A fuzzy graph G is fuzzy Hamiltonian if there exists some $\alpha > 0$, such that the crisp graph G_α is Hamiltonian. This connects fuzzy Hamiltonicity directly to classical Hamiltonian graph theory. Hamiltonicity is the property of a graph of containing a cycle that visits every

vertex exactly once. When we say “is Hamiltonian”, means the graph G contains a Hamiltonian cycle. It helps us to understand Hamiltonicity of a fuzzy graph using classical graph theory. Some classical sufficient conditions for Hamiltonicity are: 1) Dirac theorem: if $|V(G)| = n \geq 3$, minimum degree $\delta(G) \geq n/2$, n -number of vertices [9]. Ore’s theorem: if for every pair of non-adjacent vertices (u, v) , $d_u + d_v \geq n$ [10]. Fuzzy Hamiltonian graphs are used in communication networks with uncertain links, transportation systems under varying reliability, molecular topology and decision-making problems. Effective Eulerian and fuzzy Hamiltonian graph were studied in [11]. A graph G is Hamiltonian if and only if its closure is Hamiltonian. Sufficient conditions for Hamiltonian fuzzy graphs given in [12]. A graph G is Hamilton-connected (HC) if every two vertices of G are connected by a Hamiltonian path. All complete graphs are Hamilton connected and thus Hamiltonian [13]. Characteristics of fuzzy wheel and Hamiltonian graph with fuzzy rule were studied in [14]. The algorithm for finding a Hamiltonian cycle in an intuitionistic fuzzy graph (IFG), based on the theories of intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFSs) and of index matrices (IMs) were proposed in [15]. A graph is said to be hypo Hamiltonian if for each $v \in V(G)$, the vertex sub graph $G-v$ is Hamiltonian [16]. Complete fuzzy graph K_{2n+1} can be decomposed to n Hamiltonian fuzzy cycles [17]. Shortest distances in Hamiltonian fuzzy cycles computed in [18]. The fuzzy Hamiltonian cycles constitute the routes for transportation network and starting point, which gives the shortest travel time [19]. Sombor index in fuzzy graph was computed in [20] using degrees and membership values of vertices in G .

The first, second Zagreb polynomials and hyper-Zagreb polynomials can be defined as [21]

$$M_1(G, x) = \sum_{u \in V} x^{\sigma(u) (d_G(u))^2}. \quad (1)$$

$$M_2(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E} x^{\frac{1}{2}[\sigma(u)d_G(u) + \sigma(v)d_G(v)]}. \quad (2)$$

$$HM_1(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E} x^{[\sigma(u) d_G(u) + \sigma(v) d_G(v)]^2}. \quad (3)$$

$$HM_2(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E} x^{[\sigma(u) d_G(u) \times \sigma(v) d_G(v)]^2} \quad (4)$$

where $d_G(u)$ and $\sigma(u)$ is the degree and membership value of the vertex u respectively in the fuzzy graph G .

Forgotten polynomial is defined as

$$F(G, x) = \sum_{v \in V} x^{[\sigma(v)d_G(v)]^3}. \quad (5)$$

Harmonic polynomial can be defined as

$$H(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E} x^{\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{[\sigma(u)d_G(u) + \sigma(v)d_G(v)]}}. \quad (6)$$

Randic polynomial can be defined as

$$R(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E} x^{\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{[\sigma(u)d_G(u) \times \sigma(v)d_G(v)]}}. \quad (7)$$

The symbols, notations are standard and taken from [22-24]. In this paper first, second Zagreb polynomials, hyper first, second Zagreb polynomials, forgotten polynomial, harmonic polynomial and Randic polynomial are investigated for fuzzy Hamiltonian graph.

Materials and Methods:

The fuzzy degree of a vertex u in G is defined as the sum of all the weights of edges corresponding to the vertex u that is $d_G(u) = \sum_{uv \in E} \mu(u, v)$. The Hamiltonian path is represented in figure (1) and Hamiltonian cycle in fig. (2). The fuzzy Hamiltonian graph is shown in figure (3). Fuzzy Hamiltonian graph in figure (4) with membership values of vertices and edges is used to compute topological polynomials [25].

Results and Discussion:

The a-b-c-d is a Hamiltonian path in figure (1) and a-b-c-d-e-a is Hamiltonian cycle in fig. (2). Consider fuzzy Hamiltonian graph (fig.4), in which we have three Hamiltonian cycles as: 12345671, 13572461, 14736251. The

vertices with membership values are $\sigma(0.7)$, $\sigma(0.6)$, $\sigma(0.7)$, $\sigma(0.5)$, $\sigma(0.3)$, $\sigma(0.7)$ and $\sigma(0.6)$ and the degrees for vertices are:

$$d_G(V_1) = 0.4+0.5+0.6+0.7+0.8+0.9 = 3.9,$$

$$d_G(V_2) = 0.9+0.55+0.65+0.75+0.85+0.3 = 4,$$

$$d_G(V_3) = 0.3+0.8+0.25+0.35+0.95+0.45 = 3.1,$$

$$d_G(V_4) = 0.45+0.85+0.7+0.1+0.2+0.15 = 2.45,$$

$$d_G(V_5) = 0.15+0.95+0.75+0.6+0.8+0.3 = 3.55,$$

$$d_G(V_6) = 0.3+0.2+0.35+0.65+0.5+0.4 = 2.4$$

$$\text{and } d_G(V_7) = 0.4+0.55+0.25+0.1+0.8+0.4 = 2.5.$$

The membership values of edges are:

$$\mu(1, 2)=0.9, \mu(2,3)=0.3, \mu(3, 4)=0.45, \mu(4, 5)=0.15, \mu(5, 6)=0.3, \mu(6,7)=0.4 \text{ and } \mu(7,1)=0.4.$$

Theorem 1. First Zagreb polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph is $x^{10.65}+x^{9.6}+x^{6.727}+x^{3.1}+x^{3.781}+x^{4.032}+x^{3.75}$.

Proof. Using membership values of vertices and edges from figure (4), we have first Zagreb polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph

$$\begin{aligned} F_{HM_1}(G,x) &= \sum_{u \in V} x^{\sigma(u) (d_G(u))^2} \\ &= x^{0.7 \times (3.9)^2} + x^{0.6 \times (4)^2} + x^{0.7 \times (3.1)^2} + x^{0.5 \times (2.45)^2} + x^{0.3 \times (3.55)^2} + x^{0.7 \times (2.4)^2} + x^{0.6 \times (2.5)^2} \\ &= x^{10.65} + x^{9.6} + x^{6.727} + x^{3.1} + x^{3.781} + x^{4.032} + x^{3.75}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2. Second Zagreb polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph is $x^{3.276} + x^{2.604} + x^{1.329} + x^{0.652} + x^{0.8946} + x^{1.26} + x^{2.047}$.

Proof. Using membership values of vertices and edges from figure (4), we get second Zagreb polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph

$$\begin{aligned} F_{HM_2}(G,x) &= \sum_{uv \in E} x^{\frac{1}{2}[\sigma(u)d_G(u) \times \sigma(v)d_G(v)]} \\ &= x^{\frac{1}{2}[(0.7)3.9 \times (0.6)4]} + x^{\frac{1}{2}[(0.6)4 \times (0.7)3.1]} + x^{\frac{1}{2}[(0.7)3.1 \times (0.5)2.45]} + x^{\frac{1}{2}[(0.5)2.45 \times (0.3)3.55]} + x^{\frac{1}{2}[(0.3)3.55 \times (0.7)2.4]} + x^{\frac{1}{2}[(0.7)2.4 \times (0.6)2.5]} + x^{\frac{1}{2}[(0.6)2.5 \times (0.7)3.9]} \\ &= x^{3.276} + x^{2.604} + x^{1.329} + x^{0.652} + x^{0.8946} + x^{1.26} + x^{2.047}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3. First hyper Zagreb polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph is $x^{26.32} + x^{20.88} + x^{11.53} + x^{5.244} + x^{7.535} + x^{10.12} + x^{17.89}$.

Proof. First hyper Zagreb polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph

$$\begin{aligned} F_{HHM_1}(G,x) &= \sum_{uv \in E} x^{[\sigma(u) d_G(u) + \sigma(v) d_G(v)]^2} \\ &= x^{[(0.7)3.9 + (0.6)4]^2} + x^{[(0.6)4 + (0.7)3.1]^2} + x^{[(0.7)3.1 + (0.5)2.45]^2} + x^{[(0.5)2.45 + (0.3)3.55]^2} + x^{[(0.3)3.55 + (0.7)2.4]^2} + x^{[(0.7)2.4 + (0.6)2.5]^2} + x^{[(0.6)2.5 + (0.7)3.9]^2} \\ &= x^{26.32} + x^{20.88} + x^{11.53} + x^{5.244} + x^{7.535} + x^{10.12} + x^{17.89}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4. Second hyper Zagreb polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph is $x^{42.93} + x^{27.12} + x^{7.066} + x^{1.703} + x^{3.201} + x^{6.351} + x^{16.76}$.

Proof. Second hyper Zagreb polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph

$$\begin{aligned} F_{HHM_2}(G,x) &= \sum_{uv \in E} x^{[\sigma(u) d_G(u) \times \sigma(v) d_G(v)]^2} \\ &= x^{[(0.7)3.9 \times (0.6)4]^2} + x^{[(0.6)4 \times (0.7)3.1]^2} + x^{[(0.7)3.1 \times (0.5)2.45]^2} + x^{[(0.5)2.45 \times (0.3)3.55]^2} + x^{[(0.3)3.55 \times (0.7)2.4]^2} + x^{[(0.7)2.4 \times (0.6)2.5]^2} + x^{[(0.6)2.5 \times (0.7)3.9]^2} \\ &= x^{42.93} + x^{27.12} + x^{7.066} + x^{1.703} + x^{3.201} + x^{6.351} + x^{16.76}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 5. The forgotten polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph is $x^{20.35} + x^{13.82} + x^{10.22} + x^{1.838} + x^{1.207} + x^{4.742} + x^{3.375}$.

Proof. Using membership values of vertices and edges from figure (4), we get forgotten polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph

$$\begin{aligned} F_{HF}(G,x) &= \sum_{v \in V} x^{[\sigma(v)d_G(v)]^3} \\ &= x^{[(0.7)3.9]^3} + x^{[(0.6)4]^3} + x^{[(0.7)3.1]^3} + x^{[(0.5)2.45]^3} + x^{[(0.3)3.55]^3} + x^{[(0.7)2.4]^3} + x^{[(0.6)2.5]^3} \\ &= x^{20.35} + x^{13.82} + x^{10.22} + x^{1.838} + x^{1.207} + x^{4.742} + x^{3.375}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 6. Harmonic polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph is $x^{0.0975} + x^{0.1094} + x^{0.1472} + x^{0.2183} + x^{0.1822} + x^{0.1572} + x^{0.1182}$.

Proof. Harmonic polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{HH}(G,x) &= \sum_{uv \in E} \frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[\sigma(u)d_G(u) + \sigma(v)d_G(v)]}} \\
 &= \frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[(0.7)3.9 + (0.6)4]}} + \frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[(0.6)4 + (0.7)3.1]}} + \\
 &\frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[(0.7)3.1 + (0.5)2.45]}} + \frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[(0.5)2.45 + (0.3)3.55]}} + \\
 &\frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[(0.3)3.55 + (0.7)2.4]}} + \frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[(0.7)2.4 + (0.6)2.5]}} + \\
 &\frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[(0.6)2.5 + (0.7)3.9]}} \\
 &= x^{0.0975} + x^{0.1094} + x^{0.1472} + x^{0.2183} + \\
 &x^{0.1822} + x^{0.1572} + x^{0.1182}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 7. Randic polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph is $x^{0.1953} + x^{0.2191} + x^{0.3066} + x^{0.4423} + x^{0.3738} + x^{0.3215} + x^{0.247}$.

Proof. Randic polynomial in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{HR}(G,x) &= \sum_{uv \in E} \frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[\sqrt{\sigma(u)d_G(u) \times \sigma(v)d_G(v)}]}} \\
 &= \frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[\sqrt{(0.7)3.9 \times (0.6)4]}}} + \frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[\sqrt{(0.6)4 \times (0.7)3.1]}}} + \\
 &\frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[\sqrt{(0.7)3.1 \times (0.5)2.45]}}} + \frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[\sqrt{(0.5)2.45 \times (0.3)3.55]}}} + \\
 &\frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[\sqrt{(0.3)3.55 \times (0.7)2.4]}}} + \frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[\sqrt{(0.7)2.4 \times (0.6)2.5]}}} + \\
 &\frac{1}{x^2 \frac{1}{[\sqrt{(0.6)2.5 \times (0.7)3.9]}}} \\
 &= x^{0.1953} + x^{0.2191} + x^{0.3066} + x^{0.4423} + \\
 &x^{0.3738} + x^{0.3215} + x^{0.247}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1. Hamilton path.

Fig.2. Fuzzy Hamilton graph.

Fig.3. Fuzzy Hamilton graph.

Figure 4. Fuzzy Hamilton graph.

Conclusion:

A graph containing a Hamiltonian cycle is called a Hamiltonian graph. If the membership values of vertices and edges in fuzzy Hamiltonian graph are known then the topological polynomials can be computed. In this paper first, second Zagreb polynomials, hyper first, second Zagreb polynomials, forgotten polynomial, harmonic polynomial and Randic polynomial are obtained for fuzzy Hamiltonian graph.

References:

1. A.K.Sharma, B.V.Padamwar and C.L.Dewangan, (2013) Trends in fuzzy graphs, International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology,2(9) (4636-4640).
2. M.R.Nidhin, A.Shukla, (2024) The versatility of fuzzy graph in addressing uncertainty in data, International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology,4(2) 863-868.
3. A.Nagoorgani, V.T.Chandrasekaran, (2010) A first look at fuzzy relation theory, Allied Publishers Pvt.Ltd.
4. S.Lavanya, S.Ramya, (2018) Edge domination in some special classes of fuzzy graphs, International Journal of Mathematics and its Applications,6(2-A) 141-144.
5. K.R.S.Narayan, M.S.Sunitha, (2012) Connectivity in a fuzzy graph and complement ,Gen.Math.Notes,9(1) 38-43.
6. A.Muneera, T.T.Nageswara Rao and R.V.N.Srinivasa Rao, (2019) Fuzzy Eulerian and Fuzzy Hamiltonian graphs with their applications, International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering,8(4) 7995-7997.
7. M.Vijaya, A.Kannan, (2017) Number of Hamiltonian fuzzy cycles in cubic fuzzy graphs with vertices n , International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Virtual Institute,117(6) 91-98.
8. W.R.Hamilton, (1835) Irish Mathematician, Hamiltonian Mechanics and Hamiltonians,
9. P. Dirac, (1952) A sufficient condition for a graph to be Hamiltonian, Graph Theory,
10. O.Ore, (1960) Note on Hamiltonian circuits. Am Math Mon, 67:55,
11. A.Nagoorgani, R.J.Hussain, (2008) Effective fuzzy Euler and fuzzy Hamiltonian graph, International Review of Fuzzy Mathematics,3(1) 55-68.
12. R.Li, (2022) Sufficient conditions for Hamiltonian fuzzy graphs, Annals of Pure and Applied Mathematics,26(1) 15-17.
13. S.Prabhu,Y.S.Nisha,M.Cary, M.Arulperumjothi and X.Li, (2024) On detour index of join of Hamiltonian-connected graphs, Ars Combinatoria,160 195-203.
14. D.Nisha, B.Srividhya, C(2019) characteristics of fuzzy wheel graph and Hamiltonian graph with fuzzy rule, International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development,3(6) 1061-1064.
15. V.Traneva, S.Tranev, (2020) Intuitionistic fuzzy Hamiltonian cycle index matrix, Proceeding of the Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information System, IEEE Catalogue number CFP2085N-ART,PTI, 345-348.
16. M.A.Shah, (2013) A study on hypo Hamiltonian graphs, African Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science Research,6(2) 16-19.

17. V.Kamalakaran, (2015) Hamiltonian decomposition of complete fuzzy graphs and some results using fuzzy matrices, International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering and Technology,2(1) 413-418.
18. A.Parthiban, V.Kalalakanna and M.Senthilkumar, (2016) Computing shortest distance of Hamiltonian fuzzy cycles using eigen values, International Journal of Current Trends in Engineering and Technology,2(1) 13-17.
19. E.Cakir, Z.Ulukan and T.Acarman, (2021) Shortest fuzzy Hamiltonian cycle on transportation network using minimum vertex degree and time dependent Dijkstra's algorithm, Science Direct IFAC papers online,54-2, 348-353.
20. B.Some, M.Mondal and A.Pal, (2024) Numerous bounds and significance of Sombor index in fuzzy graph, Journal of Applied Mathematics and Computing, Springer.
21. Sk. R.Islam, M.Pal, (2023) F-index for fuzzy graph with applications, TWMS Journal of Applied and Engineering Mathematics, 13(2) 514-530.
22. M.Pal, S.Samanta and G.Ghorai, (2020) Modern Trends in Fuzzy Graph Theory, Springer,
23. J.A.Bondy and U.S.R.Murty, (1976) Graph Theory with Applications, Macmillan, London and Elsevier, New York
24. G.Chen, T.T.Phan, (2001) Introduction to Fuzzy sets, Fuzzy logic and Fuzzy control systems, CRC Press, Boca Raton, Lodon,
25. G.Nirmala, M.Vijaya, (2012) Hamiltonian fuzzy cycles on K_{2n+1} fuzzy graph, International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications,2(1) 1-6.